

Supplementary File 1

The median, mean, SD, Q1 and Q3 Dice Similarity Coefficient for each structure

Structure	median	mean	SD	Q1	Q3
Aorta	0.90	0.86	0.11	0.86	0.92
Pulmonary Artery	0.83	0.79	0.13	0.78	0.86
Inferior Vena Cava	0.69	0.67	0.13	0.59	0.77
Superior Vena Cava	0.75	0.74	0.10	0.67	0.82
Left main coronary artery	0.42	0.39	0.19	0.25	0.54
Left anterior descending artery	0.45	0.42	0.19	0.29	0.57
Left circumflex artery	0.36	0.33	0.19	0.16	0.47
Right coronary artery	0.38	0.38	0.20	0.25	0.55
Left Atrium	0.88	0.82	0.18	0.83	0.91
Right Atrium	0.88	0.83	0.16	0.85	0.91
Left Ventricle	0.88	0.83	0.14	0.79	0.92
Right Ventricle	0.86	0.82	0.15	0.82	0.90
Left Ventricle Septal Wall	0.53	0.46	0.21	0.34	0.62
Left Ventricle Inferior Wall	0.26	0.28	0.19	0.12	0.43
Left Ventricle Anterior Wall	0.36	0.33	0.20	0.14	0.50
Left Ventricle Lateral Wall	0.55	0.50	0.20	0.43	0.63
Aortic Valve	0.15	0.21	0.21	0.00	0.34
Pulmonic Valve	0.19	0.23	0.22	0.00	0.39
Tricuspid Valve	0.13	0.19	0.17	0.03	0.31
Mitral Valve	0.18	0.23	0.19	0.07	0.37
Sinoatrial Node	0.27	0.30	0.27	0.00	0.52
Atrioventricular Node	0.29	0.31	0.27	0.03	0.54
Bronchus	0.58	0.56	0.12	0.47	0.66
Spinal canal	0.82	0.80	0.08	0.76	0.86
Heart	0.93	0.93	0.02	0.91	0.94
Trachea	0.77	0.73	0.16	0.66	0.84
Stomach	0.78	0.73	0.17	0.64	0.88
Oesophagus	0.75	0.73	0.07	0.69	0.78
Right Lung	0.96	0.95	0.03	0.93	0.97
Left Lung	0.96	0.95	0.03	0.94	0.97
ICD can/generator	0.83	0.81	0.09	0.77	0.87

The median, mean, SD, Q1 and Q3 Median Distance to Agreement (in mm) for each structure

Structure	median	mean	SD	Q1	Q3
Aorta	0.1	0.7	3.0	0.0	0.1
Pulmonary Artery	0.2	0.5	1.3	0.2	0.2
Inferior Vena Cava	0.4	0.8	1.0	0.3	0.8
Superior Vena Cava	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.3
Left main coronary artery	1.4	2.5	3.0	0.7	2.6
Left anterior descending artery	0.4	1.4	2.6	0.2	1.2
Left circumflex artery	0.7	1.8	3.1	0.3	2.0
Right coronary artery	0.4	3.2	6.5	0.2	2.9
Left Atrium	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3
Right Atrium	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2
Left Ventricle	0.3	0.6	0.9	0.2	0.4
Right Ventricle	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3
Left Ventricle Septal Wall	0.3	2.8	8.6	0.2	0.5
Left Ventricle Inferior Wall	3.0	7.6	10.4	0.8	10.6
Left Ventricle Anterior Wall	0.7	6.5	10.1	0.3	10.0
Left Ventricle Lateral Wall	0.3	3.2	10.1	0.2	0.5
Aortic Valve	4.9	7.2	7.8	2.2	9.0
Pulmonic Valve	4.1	5.8	4.9	2.0	8.3
Tricuspid Valve	6.0	7.7	8.6	1.6	9.9
Mitral Valve	4.2	5.9	6.2	0.9	8.1
Sinoatrial Node	4.5	8.8	12.5	2.0	10.8
Atrioventricular Node	4.2	7.9	10.4	1.9	10.0
Bronchus	0.3	1.5	3.2	0.2	0.9
Spinal canal	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2
Heart	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.3
Trachea	0.2	0.6	1.4	0.1	0.4
Stomach	0.3	1.9	4.9	0.2	0.5
Oesophagus	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
Right Lung	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
Left Lung	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
ICD can/generator	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.5

The median, mean, SD, Q1 and Q3 95th percentile symmetric distance to agreement (HD95) (in mm) for each structure

Structure	median	mean	SD	Q1	Q3
Aorta	1.5	10.1	22.2	1.0	2.2
Pulmonary Artery	6.5	9.7	9.3	3.8	12.6
Inferior Vena Cava	7.7	9.9	7.1	4.9	12.1
Superior Vena Cava	9.0	12.6	11.2	4.0	18.5
Left main coronary artery	7.5	11.6	10.1	4.4	15.6
Left anterior descending artery	6.6	11.3	10.6	3.2	18.6
Left circumflex artery	8.7	11.1	8.4	5.4	14.2
Right coronary artery	10.5	13.9	13.0	3.7	16.7
Left Atrium	4.2	6.7	5.9	2.9	8.2
Right Atrium	3.2	3.6	1.8	2.3	4.5
Left Ventricle	4.1	6.0	4.8	2.8	7.8
Right Ventricle	3.3	4.4	3.5	2.2	5.2
Left Ventricle Septal Wall	7.7	12.5	13.7	4.7	13.0
Left Ventricle Inferior Wall	29.9	32.7	21.1	13.7	47.9
Left Ventricle Anterior Wall	26.1	29.9	21.1	9.9	48.2
Left Ventricle Lateral Wall	7.9	12.9	14.2	4.9	13.5
Aortic Valve	17.0	18.6	10.7	10.8	22.8
Pulmonic Valve	14.6	17.5	11.1	9.2	22.4
Tricuspid Valve	17.1	18.9	11.6	10.1	24.1
Mitral Valve	15.7	16.3	8.8	9.5	20.4
Sinoatrial Node	12.0	15.4	13.9	7.6	19.3
Atrioventricular Node	11.0	14.2	11.8	6.4	17.9
Bronchus	16.5	18.9	11.8	10.0	24.7
Spinal canal	1.9	5.5	9.8	1.2	3.3
Heart	4.4	5.2	2.8	3.4	6.1
Trachea	4.0	7.4	7.8	2.0	10.5
Stomach	17.0	28.6	30.0	6.0	41.6
Oesophagus	3.3	7.2	9.6	1.9	9.1
Right Lung	1.1	1.4	1.1	0.7	1.8
Left Lung	1.1	1.5	1.2	0.7	1.8
ICD can/generator	4.6	5.7	4.3	2.7	6.7

Supplementary File 2

Guidelines for critical structure contouring in STereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation (STAR)

Heat maps with percentage agreement, with red being 100% agreement, per voxel between centres were generated using an in-house developed C++ tool.

Whole Heart:

Superiorly, the whole heart starts just inferior to the left pulmonary artery. For simplification, a round structure to include the great vessels as well can be delineated. Inferiorly, the heart blends with the diaphragm. Since cardiac vessels run in the fatty tissue within the pericardium, this should be included in the contours, even if there is no heart muscle visible in that area.(1)

Chambers:

The anatomical landmarks for delineating the four chambers are previously been described.(2) The left auricle is part of the left atrium.

Segments of the Left ventricle wall

In cardiology, the recommendation is to divide the myocardium into 17 segments.(3) However this is quite difficult on available CT-scans. To simplify the segmentation of the left ventricle and with respect to the myocardial perfusion by the respective coronary arteries, the myocardium is divided into 4 segments (or areas): an anterior (green), inferior (orange), septal (red) and lateral (cyan) segment as previously described. Although different strategies are reported to delineate the myocardial walls a contrast-enhanced CT is recommended to contour the true thickness of the wall.(2) If in the future auto-segmentation is feasible, this should be implemented.(4)

Valves

A contrast-enhanced CT is mandatory to contour the valves.(1) We recommend using axial, sagittal and coronal planes to contour the valves 3-dimensionally.

The aortic valve is found within the ascending aorta and seen in cross-section on axial CT. In a contrast scan, the leaflets typically create a “Y” within the lumen of the vessel. The angle of the valve can be seen on the coronal view.

The *pulmonic valve* is found within the pulmonary trunk and seen in cross-section on axial CT. In a contrast scan, the leaflets typically create an “X” within the lumen of the vessel. The angle of the valve can be seen on the sagittal view

The *tricuspid valve* is located between the right atrium and ventricle. It is difficult to see, but it is defined as the area where the blood pool between the atrium and ventricle is shared.

The *mitral valve* is located between the left atrium and ventricle. It is difficult to see, but it is defined as the area where the blood pool between the atrium and ventricle is shared.

Coronary arteries

Contouring the coronary arteries are complex due to the anatomical variation. Proximal parts of the arteries are more at risk for major complications. Guidelines are adjusted from Duane et al.(5) A contrast-enhanced CT is mandatory.

Left main coronary artery: From the left lateral ascending aorta running between the left atrium and the pulmonary artery to the bifurcation into left anterior descending and circumflex coronary arteries (~1.5 cm in length).

Left anterior descending coronary artery: from the end of the left main coronary artery passing anteriorly behind the pulmonary artery. It then descends anterolaterally in the anterior interventricular groove and continues in the interventricular groove and extends to the apex. Approximately 5 cm should at least be contoured. On axial view the artery can first move cranially before it descends.

Left Circumflex coronary artery: From the end of the left main coronary artery running in the left atrioventricular groove for approximately 2 cm in length and then running along the left atrioventricular groove posteriorly extending to the crux of the heart. Approximately 5 cm should at least be contoured

Right coronary artery: From the anterior aspect of the ascending aorta descending in the right atrioventricular groove to the acute heart border (horizontal heart border extending from the lower right edge of the heart to the apex formed mainly by the right ventricle) and then running medially along the right atrioventricular groove posteriorly to the crux of the heart. Approximately 5 cm should at least be contoured. On axial view the artery can first move cranially before it descends.

Nodes

The area of the sinoatrial node and the atrioventricular node are not visible on a CT-scan. Therefore the delineation guidelines by Loap et al should be used.(6) Step by step delineation is described in fig 1 and fig 2 of the paper.

Aorta:

The Aorta is contoured as one structure. Starting from the left ventricle, the ascending aorta continues in the aortic arch and then descends to approximately 3 cm below the diaphragm.

Vena Cava Superior:

The Vena cava superior starts from the right ventricle and will be contoured till the level of the aortic arch.

Vena Cava Inferior:

The Vena cava Inferior starts caudally from the vena cava superior at the right ventricle. It will be contoured until the hilus of the liver.

Lungs:

limited to the air-inflated lung parenchyma without inclusion of the fluid and atelectasis visible on the CT image. Automated contouring tools can be used; however, appropriate thresholds, specific to each CT scan, should be chosen. Reviewing and editing the auto contoured structures is always required. The proximal bronchial tree should be excluded, and small sized vessels (<1 cm or vessels beyond the hilar region) should be included.(7)

Trachea:

The trachea is contoured cranially from the aortic arch till it divides in the left and right main bronchus at the carina.(7)

Main bronchus:

The main bronchus can be contoured using mediastinal windows on the CT scan to correspond to the mucosal, submucosa, and cartilage rings and airway channels associated with these structures. It can be contoured as one structure.(7)

Oesophagus:

The oesophagus should be contoured using mediastinal windowing on CT to correspond to the mucosa, submucosa, and all muscular layers out to the fatty adventitia. Cranial the oesophagus contour should begin at the level of aortic arch and continue including the gastroesophageal junction (GEJ) until it ends at the stomach.(7)

Stomach:

The stomach, separated into cardia (near the heart), fundus, body, and antrum and pylorus, should be contoured as 1 organ. The cardia begins caudal to the GEJ. The gastric fundus, the most cephalad portion of the stomach, abuts the left hemi diaphragm, and is to the left and superior to the cardia. The body is the central, largest portion of the stomach and the antrum is the gateway into the pylorus, the sphincter opening into the duodenum.(8)

Spinal Canal:

The spinal canal should be contoured according to the bony limits. The contour can start from the level of the aortic arch until 3 cm under the diaphragm.

ICD can/generator:

The device will be clearly visible on the planning-CT. If possible post-processing techniques such as metal artefact reduction algorithms should be used to correctly delineate the ICD can/generator.

References:

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